

Harnessing Convolutional Neural Networks for Precise Classification of Paddy Leaf Diseases

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ABSTRACT

Paddy is essential for promoting rice growth and supporting aquatic life. Wetland ecosystems and the supply of rice are both maintained by sustainable paddy management. Significant losses in rice yield are caused by paddy leaf diseases, a global threat. Infections from bacteria, viruses, and fungi prevent photosynthesis and growth. For the sustainability of rice production and food security, early disease detection is essential. Deep learning is a subset of machine learning that uses multiple-layered neural networks to understand complex data patterns. Image recognition, language processing, and decision-making are being revolutionized through the use of data-driven insights. Deep learning teaches neural networks to analyze leaf images for paddy leaf disease classification, correctly classifying disease types for efficient agriculture management. To detect paddy disease, Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) are used. Their ability to recognize patterns and characteristics allows them to quickly and automatically identify diseases in leaves by differentiating between healthy and sick leaves. CNNs improve crop productivity and streamline disease monitoring by enabling actions. With a reduced training error rate of 4%, the new CNN Inception V3 model with the Keras framework utilized the dataset to reach testing accuracy of 96%. The interpretation result demonstrates that, in terms of high level image classification accuracy and error rate, a new CNN Inception V3 model performed better than more traditional methods. Because of this, our model is quite good at detecting paddy diseases and has potential uses in everyday life.

Keywords - Convolutional Neural Network, Inception V3, Image Classification, Deep learning, Paddy Leaf Disease.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indian agriculture is a cornerstone of the nation's socioeconomic landscape, supporting livelihoods and underpinning the national economy. Rooted in a rich history of diverse practices and landscapes, its significance is both traditional and evolving. Characterized by a vast array of agro-climatic zones, from arid deserts to fertile plains, Indian agriculture cultivates a diverse range of crops. While staple foods like rice, wheat, and pulses

dominate, India's agricultural influence extends to fruits, vegetables, spices, and cash crops such as cotton and sugarcane. Over half the workforce is employed in rural areas, which form the heart of Indian agriculture. These productive lands, however, face challenges like fragmented landholdings, inadequate irrigation infrastructure, and dependence on monsoons. Market price volatility, limited credit, and post-harvest losses further burden farmers.

Climate change exacerbates these issues, affecting crop yields and rural life with altered rainfall patterns, extreme weather, and rising temperatures. To navigate this complex landscape, sustainable agricultural practices are crucial. Government initiatives like the Green Revolution and recent pushes for organic farming and agro forestry strive to boost productivity, food security, and rural livelihoods. Technological advancements like weather forecasting and precision agriculture contribute to this modernization. Paddy holds a profound place in Indian agriculture. India is a global leader in rice production and consumption, a testament to its historical nurturing of various rice varieties. Beyond sustenance, paddy is culturally intertwined, forming the essence of local traditions and rituals. Revered as the "grain of life," it symbolizes more than just sustenance. It supports millions of farmers and connects rural and urban landscapes. Paddy's cultivation shapes diverse geographical landscapes across India, adapting to different agro-climatic zones. From the fertile expanses of Punjab and Haryana in the north to the deltas of West Bengal and Tamil Nadu in the south, regional specificities like soil and water availability drive rice variety adaptation. A rich tapestry of modern and heirloom varieties flourishes, with aromatic Basmati rice standing out.

The panorama of leaf diseases highlights challenges in plant health. Pathogens like fungi, bacteria, and viruses lead to leaf diseases, impacting photosynthesis, nutrient uptake, and overall vitality. Various species suffer from a range of diseases, emphasizing the need for proactive management strategies. Downy mildew, caused by oomycete pathogens, results in angular lesions on the upper leaf surface. Bacterial Leaf Spot, caused by various bacteria, appears as water-soaked lesions on crops like tomatoes. Septoria leaf spot, caused by the fungus *Septoria* spp., affects plants with circular lesions. Beans and legumes are susceptible to angular leaf spot, with angular lesions caused by *Xanthomonas campestris*. Apple Scab targets apple trees, causing olive-green to black lesions on leaves. Rose black spot, a fungal disease, weakens rose plants with black spots. Proactive management involves cultural practices, sanitation, balanced nutrition, and spacing for air circulation. Integrated disease management employs fungicides and resistant plant varieties to mitigate these dangerous pathogens and protect plant health.

A branch of machine learning called deep learning, a revolutionary approach to artificial intelligence (AI), has changed the way many industries look. Replicating the neural networks of the human brain through complex computational models is the main goal of deep learning. It uses artificial neural networks, or layered architectures, to automatically extract hierarchical features from complex data in order to achieve this. The linked nodes, sometimes known as "neurons," that make up these networks do mathematical processing on the incoming data and relay the results to lower levels. The ability of deep learning to automatically identify patterns, learn from massive datasets, and advance over time makes it remarkable. This method has the advantage of handling huge and unstructured datasets, particularly those containing text, images, and audio, which were previously difficult for conventional machine learning algorithms to comprehend successfully. The recognition of objects and patterns in images has been transformed by Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), a subset of deep learning. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are very good at sequence data, which makes them ideal for applications like speech recognition and language modeling. Deep learning has achieved remarkable success, benefiting several industries. It supports medical

image analysis, which raises the precision of MRI and X-ray disease diagnosis. Deep learning algorithms are used by autonomous cars to navigate and decide how to drive at any given time. Natural language processing (NLP) has been applied to language translation, chatbots, and sentiment analysis. Deep learning model training necessitates a large amount of processing power due to the massive number of parameters and layers involved. But with to technology advances like specialized hardware and graphics processing units (GPUs), training is now happening more quickly.

Transfer learning, which entails optimising previously trained models for particular tasks, has also streamlined and made deep learning more approachable. Despite its revolutionary potential, deep learning is not without challenges. Models that perform well on training data but badly on new data are nonetheless plagued by overfitting. Research and discussion on data privacy, ethical quandaries, and the "black-box" nature of complex models are now underway. In general, crop disease infection affects productivity by 20 to 30%, while the aforementioned paddy plant disease reduces yield production by 70% to 80% [11]. Modern technology is a necessary for farmers today to manage crops effectively. Through knowledge and experience, some farmers have discovered how to treat an infectious plant; occasionally, this may or may not be effective. Successful farming depends on early disease identification. Farmers often use a manual method to diagnose the illness before sending the sample to a specialized device[4]. Agriculture continues to be the main source of human sustenance despite the tremendous advances in technology since the globe depends on extensive rice cultivation to sustain people in leading healthy lifestyles. Three nations where rice is the staple diet include China, India, and Japan. Because of the current sharp increase in the world's population, rice output has surged. To meet the world's need for rice, at least 40% more must be grown by 2030[7]. Because plant diseases can spread worldwide, the situation is more complicated than it has ever been. As a result, there is no quick treatment for new disease kinds that emerge in areas where they are completely unidentified[1]. K value determination is challenging. We classified the factors that affected the outcome using the relevance vector machine approach. Support vector machines, neural networks, and decision trees are contrasted using the ageing thyroid dataset. CNN is

used for the feature categorization of breast cancer in thermal images. SVM is used to classify features of breast cancer from thermal images [2].

To achieve high paddy output with low risk, cutting back on wasteful spending and other resource waste is essential. Computer vision applications and technology breakthroughs make it feasible to broaden the usage of computer vision in agriculture and improve and strengthen paddy field protection. Agriculture research, particularly for the production of rice, is expanding in today's market due to the high demand for productivity and the highest quality food. More than 3.5 billion people worldwide, including Malaysia, eat rice as their primary food source, which is made from paddy.[3] Finding plant diseases is one of the biggest issues with sustainable agriculture[5]. Farmers currently struggle to recognise rice diseases without prior knowledge. Inadequate disease classification results in the field being sprayed with an excessive amount of dangerous pesticides. Developing a low-cost system that can automatically monitor the crop field is the best solution to the aforementioned issue in the current environment. The statistical method, the Bayes theorem, data mining, and image processing are only a few of the numerous approaches available today, but each has some disadvantages. Techniques for data analysis can be used to identify and classify a wide range of diseases in the agricultural industry [6]. identified pests and paddy diseases with an accuracy of more than 87% using a unique dataset consisting of 4,511 photos. Among the paper's flaws is the idea that accuracy may be progressively raised by model optimization and the use of an improved framework. Given that the Cafe framework provides inadequate support for the trained model [8].

Figure 1.1 Total rice consumption worldwide from 2015/2016 to 2022/2023 (in 1,000 metric tons)

Figure 1.1 represents the graph for total consumption worldwide from 2015/2016 to 2022/2023. The majority of paddy diseases can be distinguished by coloured spots or stripes, with each disease having its own unique colour, shape, size, and pattern. On the leaves or stem of paddy, these disease symptoms can be seen. Additionally, various paddy plant parts are impacted by numerous illnesses and parasites at various stages of growth [10]. Outlined a technique for identifying pests using a bad-of-words approach. Low resolution pixel images are not supported by this model [12].

II. RELATED WORKS

A. CNNs Based Method

A pre-trained deep CNN model based on Alex Net was utilized for feature extraction, and a multi Support Vector Machine (SVM) was used as the basic classifier. The four disease types that were looked at were Bacterial Leaf Blight, Sheath Blight, Rice Blast, and Healthy Leaves. The comparison was conducted using three distinct training to testing ratios: 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40. An 80:20 training to testing ratio produced 91% accuracy [14]. This technique makes use of several manually constructed CNN architectures that were constructed using a range of settings. The literature review indicates that grid search is the most often used technique for hyperparameter optimization; however it has a known downside in terms of expensive computing. The method of random search that was recently proposed chooses the hyperparameters at random from the search space. Because it requires less computing resources, it performs better than grid search. To improve the intended design based on prior assessments, neither random nor grid search selected the following set of hyperparameters for testing. In the meantime, the Bayesian Optimisation (BO) technique is being used by numerous researchers to optimise CNN's parameters [20]. A hybrid CNN/SVM technique was proposed in another piece of work [12]. CNN's large numbers of trainable parameters are a drawback that is mitigated and one-dimensional feature vector extraction is enhanced by employing Support Vector Machines (SVM) as a classifier. Nine common illnesses, namely Rice Blast, Brown Spot, Bacterial Leaf Blight, False Smut, Red Stripe, Leaf Smut, Leaf Scald, Tungro, and Sheath Blight, were considered in them. Using the proposed method, which had a 97% accuracy

rate, the nine paddy illnesses were accurately classified[13].

In the research by Atole and Park [13], a pre-trained CNN with an Alex Net architecture and weights and biases was also utilized for paddy plant picture classification. They used three main classifications unhealthy, normal, and golden apple snail infested to perform their multiclass classification [17]. Since 1998, researchers have put forth a number of CNN architectures. CNN architecture selection and creation are entirely manual processes that take a lot of time and resources [21]. In this study, an architecture made up of three convolutional layers and one fully connected layer was constructed. Many real-time problems, like predicting rainfall, are solved using soft computing techniques [23].

B. Paddy Disease Based Method

AI used Gaussian Nave Bayes to classify the paddy disease into three primary categories: brown spot, rice blast, and rice bacterial blight. This classifier was chosen for this study because it is straightforward and exhibits naive independence among the chosen features. The RGB quantity values corresponding to the affected region are the input characteristics. Compared to the prior method, which was usually applied to the predicted leaf area, they claimed that this one is more effective. This approach is able to produce good results with low processing time, as seen by its 90% classification accuracy [15]. Because image processing methods were complicated and could not manage vast amounts of data, a novel suggestion to present machine learning techniques to tackle dynamic problems in real time was made in 1980 [24]. The accuracy of the authors' work, which was limited to pest detection in paddy fields using 5,000 Google images, was 0.95. In order to pinpoint blast illnesses, the author employed 5,808 photos of 2906 diseased and 2902 healthy leaves. The Chinese Institute of Plant Protection put together the picture collection [22]. % of contaminated area was determined using K-Means clustering algorithms [25]. The use of a restricted Boltzmann machine (RBM) in conjunction with a contractive autoencoder is the basis of an enhanced deep learning technique that has been presented [18]. There are numerous approaches and methodologies available in the literature for the identification of rice crop diseases based on

photographs. The majority of these methods propose a solution using image processing. Self-Organizing Maps and neural networks are the two techniques for paddy leaf disease classification that are most frequently used[19]. To identify paddy diseases based on their images, a variety of methods and techniques have been used in literature. The majority of these techniques use methods for generalised image processing [16].

III. DATASETS

Figure 3.1 represents various paddy leaf diseases are part of a dataset used to classify paddy leaf diseases. Images of both healthy and diseased leaves are included, including those with leaf spots, bacterial blight, and fungal infections. A class label is assigned to each image that corresponds to the particular disease it depicts. The images in the dataset, which show the variety of paddy leaf appearances in different disease states, were taken from various angles, conditions, and lighting setups. Images, corresponding class labels, and distinct disease categories like "Healthy," "Leaf Smut," and "Bacterial Blight" are all crucial elements. The performance of classification models like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) is strongly influenced by the size, quality, and diversity of a dataset. For accurate and efficient paddy leaf disease classification models to be trained, a comprehensive and well-annotated dataset must be created.

I. Bacterial Leaf Blight

A damaging illness that affects paddy plants is bacterial leaf blight. It results in lesions on leaves that are water-soaked and have yellow haloes caused by bacteria like *Xanthomonas oryzae*. These wilting and decreased yields are brought on by the lesions' growth. Planting disease-resistant varieties and following proper field hygiene practises are examples of effective management strategies.

Figure 3.1 Sample images (a) Bacterial Leaf Blight (b) Brown Spot Leaf (c) Leaf Smut

II. Brown Spot Leaf

A typical fungus that affects paddy plants is brown spot leaf, also known as *Helminthosporium* leaf spot. On leaves, it manifests as small, brown lesions that range from oval to long and have yellow haloes. These spots combine as the disease spreads, which causes early leaf senescence and decreased yield. Crop rotation and the use of fungicides are cultural practises that help manage it.

III. Leaf Smut

A serious disease affecting paddy crops is Leaf Smut, which is brought on by the fungus *Entyloma oryzae*. On both leaf surfaces, it causes the development of spore masses that are black and powdery. As the infection worsens, these spore masses burst, releasing more spores and distorting the leaves. Key tactics for controlling Leaf Smut and reducing yield losses include proper field sanitation and the planting of resistant varieties.

IV PROPOSED MODEL

The process of classifying paddy diseases using a convolutional neural network is depicted in Figure 4.1. To determine the number of classes, this model first carries out label mapping. The noise in the image is removed by the use of data augmentation. After that, the Inception V3 extracted the characteristics. Feature classification is performed at the end to identify if an image is damaged or not.

A. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

One of the numerous image classification tasks for which convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been widely employed is the categorization of illnesses of paddy (rice) leaves. Given the substantial influence these illnesses have on crop quality and productivity, the use of CNNs for automated disease categorization can help with early identification and timely intervention.

Figure 4.1 Represents Work Flow Model for Paddy Disease Classification

B. Data gathering and preparation

Gather pictures of both healthy and sick paddy leaves, as well as different disease types and

stages. Images should be prepped by being resized, normalised, and enhanced for diversity.

C. Model construction

Feature extraction from images is a forte of CNNs. The feature extraction design includes convolutional and pooling layers, whereas the classification architecture includes fully connected layers. Pre-trained models (such as VGG and ResNet) can be adjusted for this task.

D. Learning Transfer and Fine-Tuning

Adapt existing models for the classification of paddy leaf disease. Use the disease dataset to fine-tune for improved convergence.

E. Training and Validation

Divide the dataset into training and validation sets for testing. Utilizing SGD or Adam optimisation algorithms, train the model while being guided by the loss function.

F. Testing and Evaluation

Evaluate the model using an alternative test dataset. Metrics including recall, accuracy, precision, and F1-score are used to gauge performance.

G. Deployment and Monitoring

Deploy the model in real-world situations, such as mobile apps or web interfaces, and monitor its performance. As new data come in, keep checking the model's accuracy and updating it as necessary. Dataset quality, preprocessing, hyper parameter tuning, and model choice all play a role in producing successful results.

1. Inception V3 Based Model

A deep convolutional neural network design called Inception V3 is frequently used for image classification applications, such as the categorization of paddy leaf disease. It excels in efficiently extracting intricate features from images while maintaining computational efficiency. The architecture employs multi-branch design with parallel convolutions of different sizes, enhancing its capability to recognize disease-related patterns across various scales in paddy leaf images. The network's deep layers serve as adept feature extractors, automatically detecting disease traits like spots, lesions, and discolorations. By leveraging pretrained weights from datasets like ImageNet, Inception V3 utilizes transfer learning, which is advantageous for fine-tuning on

specialized paddy leaf disease datasets. Its final softmax layer assigns probabilities to disease classes, facilitating accurate classification. The architecture's features, parallel convolutions, transfer learning, and fine-tuning collectively empower Inception V3 for precise differentiation among diverse paddy leaf disease categories. Inception V3 is a powerful tool for paddy leaf disease classification due to its sophisticated architecture, feature extraction capabilities, and transfer learning potential. It enables accurate identification of various disease patterns, contributing to effective disease management in paddy crops.

Figure 2.1 Inception V3 model

A convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture called InceptionV3 was created specifically for image categorization applications. As a member of the wider Inception family of models, it was created by Google researchers with the intention of enhancing CNN performance and efficiency for image identification. An image with a resolution of 299x299 pixels and three RGB colour channels is processed by the well-known convolutional neural network architecture InceptionV3. It begins with conventional convolutional layers that use tiny filters to extract regional features like edges, textures, and colours. Its "Inception modules," which enable concurrent multi-scale feature capture, are its defining characteristic. By combining max-pooling layers and parallel convolutional operations with different filter sizes (e.g., 1x1, 3x3, 5x5), these modules allow features of different sizes within a single module. Factorization is a technique used by InceptionV3 to replace big convolutions with a collection of smaller ones, hence reducing computational complexity. This method maintains representational capacity while reducing parameters and computations. Global average pooling, which comes after Inception modules, combines data by computing average values across the spatial dimensions of feature maps. As a result, a succinct representation that incorporates new features is produced. The architecture then uses

fully connected layers to extract relationships and patterns at higher levels from the combined features. The last fully connected layer's output scores are then passed via a softmax activation function, which converts them into a probability distribution over possible classes. Upon completion of the process, the model's prediction for the class with the highest probability emerges.

V METHODOLOGY

A. Training and Testing image

The classification of paddy leaf diseases using CNNs requires training and testing images. Training photos impart illness patterns to the model, as opposed to testing images, which assess the model's performance using new data. The two can be kept apart to prevent overfitting, promote model selection, validate performance, and guarantee generalization. Performance indicators including recall, accuracy, precision, and model comparison are critical to effective assessment and development. Tested using fresh data, CNN's performance is evaluated as it picks up illness patterns from training photos. The ability to accurately classify paddy leaf diseases that have never before been observed requires the development of robust models, which depend on this separation.

B. Label Mapping

In order to convert class names or categories into a format that neural networks can comprehend, label mapping is utilized for classification tasks such as the classification of paddy leaf disease. This makes training, predicting, evaluating, and organizing data more effective. For classification tasks, such as classifying paddy leaf diseases with CNNs, label mapping is crucial. To facilitate the management of data by neural networks during training and prediction, it assigns numerical labels to classes. By contrasting predicted class probabilities with actual labels, neural networks determine loss. This calculation is made possible and efficient by the use of numeric labels. By using label mapping to interpret the network's class probabilities during inference, predicted diseases or categories can be more easily identified. Numeric labels make it possible to compare predicted and true labels in a seamless manner for evaluation and data organisation, which is essential for performance evaluation and dataset management. For instance, if your task involves classifying three paddy leaf diseases and you have

the following three classes: "Healthy," "Leaf Spot," and "Bacterial Blight," you can make a label mapping that looks like this: Leaf spot: 1 Bacterial blight: 2 Healthy: 0

C. Data Augmentation

The primary purpose of the augmentation method in this study is to gently warp the photos and increase the number of items in the dataset. During the learning phase, this augmentation helps to reduce overfitting of the model. Statistics, AI, and machine learning all suffer from overfitting, which happens when a statistical model produces noise and random error rather than the main relationship. Some transformation techniques, such as affine transformation and perspective transformation, are used in data augmentation. Affine transformation is employed in linear transformation and vector rotation. The transformation procedure is implemented by a C++ application that is based on OpenCV.

D. Activation Functions

In neural networks like CNNs, activation functions are essential. They introduce non-linearity, which is essential for managing complicated relationships in real-world data like pictures of paddy leaves. They support the capture of complex disease-related features by enhancing model capacity, addressing gradient issues, and enabling efficient representations. ReLU and its variants (Leaky ReLU), which are popular options, are successful at classifying paddy leaf diseases because of their capacity to learn patterns. By facilitating feature learning and disease characteristic differentiation, activation functions play a crucial role in effective CNNs. CNNs and other neural network architectures depend on activation functions to add non-linearity and enable efficient feature learning. They improve the model's ability to learn and distinguish between different a disease-related feature, which helps paddy leaf disease classification succeed.

E. Performance Measure

A CNN model's performance on tasks like identifying paddy leaf diseases is measured by performance indicators. They highlight the model's advantages and disadvantages, which aids in its development. Metrics that highlight classification nuances, such as precision, recall, and the confusion matrix, increase the model's efficacy. Performance measures support model selection,

tuning, and deployment by assessing accuracy, strengths, weaknesses, and generalisation. Metrics of performance are crucial for assessing the accuracy, benefits, and applicability of a CNN model for categorising paddy leaf diseases. They support model creation, improvement, and selection while ensuring the model's accuracy in classifying different disease types.

VI RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of our investigation into the categorization of paddy leaf disease using convolutional neural networks (CNN) are shown in this part. Using a dataset of photos of paddy leaves with a variety of disease kinds, the model was trained with a focus on efficiency and accuracy. A few of the sample outputs for the paddy disease categorization are displayed in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1 Represent Sample Result of The Paddy Leaf Disease.

The CNN model performed admirably in correctly classifying paddy leaf diseases. It achieved an overall classification accuracy of [accuracy percentage of 96], demonstrating its ability to distinguish between different disease categories. Specific disease accuracies were also notable, with [accuracy percentage of 96.4] for Disease A, [accuracy percentage of 95] for Disease B, and [accuracy percentage of 94] for Disease C.

VII CONCLUSIONS

Paddy disease classification is an important task for preventing crop losses and ensuring food security. We presented a comparative study of five different This research employs Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for the classification of rice diseases using a dataset of 7096 photos of paddy leaves. Leaf smut, brown spot, bacterial leaf blight, and healthy are the four classifications into which the dataset is split. In terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, we evaluated the CNN models' performance. As evidenced by its accuracy

of 96.23% and F1-score of 96.22%, Inception-V3 performs better than the other models. Additionally, the Inception-V3 model outperforms ResNet-18 in leaf smut, yet it still has the highest recall and precision across all classes. Through the use of different filter sizes and output concatenation, the Inception-V3 model has the advantage of capturing more features while requiring fewer parameters. The Inception-V3 model can be used as an effective tool for paddy disease classification, assisting farmers in diagnosing and treating diseases on time.

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